

Studies in Indigoid Dyes. Part XXIII. Thioindigoid Dyes Derived from Dibenzofuran-2,8-disulphonic Acid

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2,3-8,7-Dibenzofurano-bis-3'-hydroxy-1'-thiophene has been prepared for the first time starting from dibenzofuran-2,8-disulphonic acid and condensed with various *o*-diketones to form indigoid dyes with the object of studying colour and its relation to chemical constitution.

In the previous communication¹ a study of colour and chemical constitution of indigoid dyes derived from dibenzofuran-2-sulphonic acid was made and bathochromic effect in those indigo dyes was observed, without exception, in the order: phenanthrene->ethylene->acenaphthylene->indol->aceanthrene-, for which an explanation also was put forward. The same sequence holds good from a study of the indigoid dyes described in the present communication. Although these are di-thioindigoid dyes obtained from a bis-thioindoxyl, the dyes are not deeper in colour than the corresponding compounds obtained from the mono-thioindoxyl derived from dibenzofuran-2-sulphonic acid. Similar result was also observed in the di-thioindigoid dyes² discussed in Parts XVI and XVII of the series.

For preparation and study of these dyes, dibenzofuran-2,8-disulphonic acid was converted into 2,8-disulphochloride³ and then to dimercaptan (I) following Corbellini and Albenza's method⁴. This dimercaptan by condensation with monochloroacetic acid was converted into dithioglycolic acid (II) and then cyclised to 2,3-8,7-dibenzofurano-bis-3'-hydroxy-1'-thiophene (III) through its acid chloride by anhydrous AlCl₃. The hydroxy-thionaphthene, thus obtained, was next condensed with *o*-diketones in acetic acid solution with traces of HCl, producing these dyes. As usual, these dyes are insoluble in ethanol, slightly soluble in acetic acid, and moderately soluble in pyridine, nitrobenzene, and xylene. These dissolve in alkaline hydrosulphite with a yellow colour and dye cotton in different shades. In H₂SO₄ (conc.) these dissolve in most of the cases with a chocolate colour.

The absorption maxima of these dyes are shown in Table I for an easy comparison of the depth of colour:

TABLE I

Name of the dye.*	λ_{max} (Xylene)
D-bis-T-3',3'-bis-indol-I	5300 Å
D-bis-T-2',2'-bis-acenaphthylene-I	5300
D-bis-T-1',1'-bis-aceanthrene-I	5200
D-bis-T-9',9'-bis-phenanthrene-I	5600
D-bis-T-bis-ethylene I-(V)	5550

*D=dibenzofurano-, T=thiophene, I=indigo.

1. *This Journal*, 1959, **36**, 609.
2. *Ibid.*, 1955, **32**, 497; 1956, **33**, 54.
3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 1412.
4. *Gazzetta*, 1931, **61**, 111.

The cyclisation of dibenzofuran-2, 8-dithioglycollic acid chloride may take place in positions 1 or 3 on one side and 7 or 9 on the other side of dibenzofuran ring. The thioindoxyl is therefore of undetermined orientation and the expression (III) is provisionally given for the compound as a working hypothesis.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dibenzofuran-2,8-dimercaptan (I).—Dibenzofuran-2,8-disulphochloride (9 g.) was reduced by Corbellini and Albenza's method⁴. The dimercaptan, thus obtained, was crystallised from petroleum ether as yellowish shining crystals, m.p. 151°, yield 3.5 g. (Found: C, 62.15; H, 3.5. $C_{12}H_8OS_2$ requires C, 62.07; H, 3.45%).

Dibenzofuran-2,8-dithioglycollic Acid (II).—The compound (I) (5 g.) was treated with cold 10% NaOH solution (20 ml), filtered from a little insoluble matter, and the filtrate treated with monochloroacetic acid (4 g.), previously neutralised with sodium carbonate. The mixture was heated on a water bath for an hour and filtered hot. The filtrate was acidified with HCl till acid to Congo red when thioglycollic acid separated as a voluminous white precipitate. After cooling it was filtered and washed. For purification, the crude thioglycollic acid was dissolved in cold aqueous sodium bicarbonate, filtered from a little insoluble matter, and the filtrate acidified. The precipitated acid was then recrystallised from a large volume of ethanol in shining white flakes, m.p. 189°. (Found: C, 55.4; H, 3.49. $C_{16}H_{12}O_5S_2$ requires C, 55.17; H, 3.44%).

2,3-8,7-Dibenzofurano-bis-3'-hydroxy-1'-thiophene (III).—Finely powdered acid (II) (5 g.) was suspended in petroleum ether (50 ml, b.p. 40-60°) and treated with PCl_3 (7.5g.).

The mixture was warmed on a water bath for an hour when most of the acid went in solution leaving a little sticky solid. The filtered solution was transferred to another vessel and cooled in a freezing mixture when gradually a thick oil separated. The supernatant layer was next carefully poured out, the oil redissolved in fresh petroleum ether (50 ml), treated with finely powdered anhydrous AlCl_3 (5 g.), and refluxed on a water-bath for 10 hours. The deep chocolate melt was then poured into crushed ice containing a little HCl (conc.). Gradually the mass became yellowish and sticky. This substance could not be obtained in a pure condition due to its easy oxidisability. For preparation of dyes, this substance was extracted with cold glacial acetic acid, filtered and the filtrate used for condensation with various *o*-diketones.

2,3-8,7-Dibenzofurano-bis-thiophene-3'-3'-bis-indol-indigo (IVa) was prepared by mixing together acetic acid solutions of isatin and 2,3-8,7-dibenzofurano-bis-3'-hydroxy-1'-thiophene and heating the mixture with HCl (conc., 1 ml) for half an hour. The solution, which became blood-red immediately, separated a deep red precipitate. This was filtered hot and the residue washed successively with acetic acid and ethanol. It was recrystallised from xylene as a deep red crystalline mass, m.p. $> 300^\circ$. It dissolves in H_2SO_4 (conc.) with a blue colour and dyes cotton in light pinkish shade. (Found: C, 67.87; H, 2.8. $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$ requires C, 67.37; H, 2.45%).

The other dyes, (*vide infra*) were obtained following the same procedure. For the sake of abbreviation "2,3-8,7-dibenzofurano-bis-thiophene" is being represented by 'R'.

R-2,2'-bi-aceanaphthylene-indigo. (IVb) was prepared from the thioindoxyl and aceanaphthenequinone and crystallised from xylene as a dark red mass; it chars at 230° and dyes cotton in pinkish shade. (Found: C, 75.8; H, 2.9. $\text{C}_{40}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3\text{S}_2$ requires C, 75.00; H, 2.5%).

R-1,1'-bis-aceanthrene-indigo (IVc) was obtained from the thioindoxyl and ace-anthraquinone as a dark brown crystalline mass. It was recrystallised from nitrobenzene, it chars at 298° and dyes cotton in coppery red shade. (Found: C, 78.12; H, 2.85. $\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3\text{S}_2$ requires C, 77.84; H, 2.7%).

R-9,9'-bis-phenanthrene-indigo (IVd) was prepared from the thioindoxyl and phenanthrenequinone and crystallised from nitrobenzene as a dark coloured mass, m.p. above 300° . It dissolves in H_2SO_4 (conc.) with a violet colour and dyes cotton in greyish shade. (Found: C, 77.12; H, 3.02. $\text{C}_{44}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3\text{S}_2$ requires, C, 76.30; H, 2.89%).

R-bis-ethylene-indigo (V) was prepared from the thioindoxyl and glyoxal sodium bisulphite and crystallised from nitrobenzene as a dark chocolate precipitate, m.p. $> 300^\circ$. It dyes cotton in greenish grey shade. [Found: C, 65.12; H, 2.01. $(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_6\text{O}_3\text{S}_2)_n$ requires C, 64.67; H, 1.8%].

The authors express their thanks to Dr. A. C. Banerjee, Principal, M. M. C. College, for his keen interest.